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“A DAY AT THE FARM”

Amid the rushes
Take a break
Embrace a pause
Feel the bliss
Of a quiet place

In a farm
That listens to your heartbeat
Whose silence truly refreshes
Your spirit to be meek

Oh farm,
I can hear the rhythm of your silence
Sing the melody of your peacefulness
Portray a picturesque sketch
Of your artistic loveliness

True joy your beauty really gives

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